

MENTORING GUIDE FOR THE BASIC EDUCATION TEACHERS OF DE LA SALLE SCHOOLS IN REGION IV-A

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ABSTRACT

Mentoring is the key for developing and sustaining a satisfying professional career. Whatever designation a person has, mentoring helps build a dynamic community while ensuring the success of each individual as they achieve personal and professional career goals. (3) Determine the personal and professional characteristics of the basic education teachers and administrators; Identify the extent on how basic education teachers benefit from mentoring; Determine if there is a significant difference in the responses of the two groups; Analyze the issues and challenges met in the mentoring process and to develop a mentoring guide based on the analysis. (4) The study utilized the descriptive method of research using the questionnaire, interview and focus group discussion. A request of an endorsement letter from the Dean addressed to the VCAs of the different Region IV-A De La Salle Schools. Respondents were 247 Basic Ed teachers of DLS Schools composed of 33 administrators and 214 teachers. (5) Findings showed that majority of the respondents manifest personal and professional characteristics of being a basic education teacher. Both respondents have both common personal and professional characteristics. There were no significant differences on the assessment done by the respondents regarding the manifestation of the benefits of mentoring relative to subject matter and evaluation techniques. (6) Majority of the respondents have developed an intensive personal relationship towards motivating students to excel. The issues and challenges during the mentoring process emanates from a workable timetable and reservation for intellectual honesty. A proposed mentoring guide was developed after a thorough scrutiny of the mentoring process.

Keywords: (7) Educational Management; Mentoring, Descriptive FGD, Philippines